

Evaluation of EEG signal processing methods for performance optimization of predictive machine learning algorithms

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Abstract— Electroencephalogram (EEG) is a biomedical operation that detects brain activity via electrodes placed around the scalp, which measure the electric field generated by active brain cells. However, only a faint source of signals effectively reaches the EEG electrodes, imposing challenges to the development of predictive algorithms for time series forecasting of EEG signals. The present proposal seeks to investigate the effects of a variety of preprocessing and data analysis techniques across multiple EEG datasets, aiming to evaluate which methods better accommodate the data for training machine learning-based predictive time series algorithms, as well as inferring which methods and parameters may be generalized throughout the different datasets and what must be adapted to each situation.

Keywords — EEG, deep learning, signal processing, parameter optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Electroencephalogram (EEG) is a type of biomedical operation that aims to detect brain activity by the placement of electrodes around the scalp surface, which measure the electric field generated by the potential difference resulting from the flow of ions through active brain cells. Such physiological source of potential difference tends to originate a relatively weak electric field, and the detected signal is also further attenuated by the presence of multiple layers of different types of cellular tissue that lie between the surface of the scalp and the cerebral cortex. As a result, only a faint source of signals effectively reaches the EEG electrodes [1].

Such limitation in data acquisition imposes challenges to the development of predictive algorithms for time series forecasting of EEG signals, which are addressed by many preprocessing techniques that have been proposed, as described in [2], who developed a standard pipeline for biomarker exploration using EEG, and [3], who describes a preprocessing pipeline for large datasets with data from many different sources. Both works are mainly centered in methods such as the application of frequency filters, detection and exclusion of noisy components via Blind Source Separation strategies, data discretization and referencing.

Although general pipelines as such may present significant improvements to signal processing, several objective techniques also impact specific aspects of the data,

which potentially implicate limitations to the performance of predictive algorithms, affecting metric values or reliability of the results. Methods of filtering signal frequencies, for instance, while popularly employed to remove frequency noise [4], invariably cause potentially harmful distortions in the data [5], and are also not recommended by some authors for potentially excluding meaningful information regarding brain activity, especially in the context of highly cognitive tasks [6, 7].

Similarly, the removal of source components considered noisy via Blind Source Separation methods, such as ICA, comprises a widely implemented strategy for data cleaning and isolation of the signal components of interest. However, it also risks removing relevant neurological information if the independent components are not properly separated, which is prone to occur, especially when the measured brain activity is composed of more physiological sources than the number of available sensors [8].

Therefore, signal processing routines for EEG must be adapted and evaluated systematically for every single application, since the optimized methods and parameters vary depending on factors such as the context of data acquisition or the different profiles of brain activity being observed.

In clinical settings, EEG methods are employed in examinations mainly concerning investigations of brain injury, epilepsy diagnostics and monitoring brain activity during anesthesia [9]. It is also recently being employed for biomarker detection of various conditions, such as Alzheimer's and depression [9, 10].

The present proposal seeks to investigate the effects of a variety of preprocessing and data analysis techniques across multiple EEG datasets, aiming to evaluate which methods better accommodate the data for training machine learning-based predictive time series algorithms, as well as inferring what methods and parameters may be generalized throughout the different datasets and what must be adapted to each situation. Finally, the obtained results may be employed to analyze properties and signal propagation dynamics, providing potential insights for efficient feature extraction processes and accurate biomedical evaluations, as well as providing means for enhancing signal modeling by machine learning algorithms via efficient fine-tuning and hyperparameter tuning strategies. The current work is the initial development phase of a fully open-source interface for real-time EEG analysis and signal prediction.

II. METHODOLOGY

Three publicly available datasets are selected for the implementation of the proposal [11], accounting for 4 different scenarios of data acquisition: a resting-state context, a cognitive task observation [12], a dataset presenting sensory stimuli [13], and a dataset of pediatric epilepsy patients [14]. The evaluated signal processing methods mainly include filtering different ranges of frequency, data scaling and normalization, and separating signal sources with ICA.

The time series forecasting algorithm employed for evaluation is a simple LSTM architecture, based on a single LSTM layer followed by a dense layer, and the predictive task is to forecast future values given a sequence of signals. Throughout the process of defining the employed methodology, slightly more complex architectures (with more LSTM and dense layers, varying the number of epochs, neurons in each layer, etc.) were also proposed and evaluated, but showed no noticeable improvements in the resulting metrics for model performance; therefore, the simplest possible architecture was selected to run all the tests in this phase of the proposal.

In order to analyze the effects of the employed signal processing strategies, algorithm performances are evaluated and compared to the results obtained using raw data. For each dataset evaluation, the complete signal recording from a single participant is split into input and output sequences that are then provided for model training. The testing phase is then performed on the sequence of signals from another participant - in summary, for each dataset, an EEG recording file is selected as the 'training' and another is selected as the 'testing' set.

For the supervised learning context, the signal sequences are split in a 'sliding window' fashion, as tuples containing subsequences of 50 input values (x) and the following n output values to be predicted (y). For the current work, n is tested for 1, 5, 10 and 30 values.

A. EEG datasets

The resting-state setting constitutes the dataset that is used as a baseline for all the subsequent analyses, since it is the only context not associated with any type of event that may provoke a neurological response, and therefore, it is considered a neutral source of information for brain activity analysis. It consists of two recordings of approximately 7 minutes, where the participants were asked to stay still and relaxed, while not performing any task or engaging with any stimulus. The sampling frequency is 1000 Hz, totaling approximately 410600 signals from each of the 31 placed electrodes.

For the cognitive task setting, the EEG recordings correspond to 60-second trials of mental arithmetic tasks (serial subtraction of two numbers). The provided data has a sampling frequency of 500 Hz, and was already preprocessed with a high-pass filter of 30 Hz and a power line notch filter of 50 Hz. To further evaluate the influence of preprocessing in model training, we additionally apply a low-pass filter of 100 Hz and remove a potentially noisy source identified via

ICA.

The sensory stimulation context consists of EEG recordings from a process of rapid presentation of images through the Rapid Serial Visual Presentation (RSVP) protocol at speed of 5 Hz. The tested data is collected from a sensor positioned in the region of the occipital lobe, where the information processing for visual activity is highest. The dataset was also preprocessed previously by the original authors, with a high-pass filter of 0.15 Hz and a low-pass of 28 Hz, and, since this data is not expected to contain significant sources of noise due to its high specificity, it is not considered necessary to detect and remove noisy components, although we evaluate the effect of removing a component that is similar to cardiac activity. The sampling frequency is 2048 Hz and trial durations are approximately 6 min.

Finally, the clinical context includes 1 hour-long recordings of pediatric participants with intractable seizures under withdrawal of medication. The EEG recordings were not previously preprocessed for this context, and the data is sampled at 256 Hz.

B. Signal processing

As previously mentioned, for the present context two preprocessing methods are evaluated: frequency filtering and exclusion of noisy components detected using ICA. For the first, a couple of band-pass filters are employed to restrict frequency oscillations to the interval between 0.01 and 100 Hz, which comprises the expected bands for most neurophysiological signals.

Additionally, two strategies of signal standardization are implemented. Since EEG signals produce very faint oscillations that are propagated in low values, the signals must be scaled up in order to provide an adequate resource for model training. This is due to the fact that values that are too close to zero cause the models' loss function to also oscillate with small values, which falsely implies that the model is succeeding in minimizing prediction errors, when, in fact, the calculated error is just varying in the same magnitude as the input signals. In order to attempt to attenuate this issue, two different loss functions are also calculated for each training epoch: mean squared error (MSE) and mean absolute error (MAE), calculated as follows:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (2)$$

While the mean squared error function is valuable for magnifying the effect of outliers in the data - which is a necessary factor to consider in EEG time series contexts - it is further approximated to zero when dealing with low baseline values, since it takes the square of each calculated error. MAE, in contrast, does not have the property of approximating the calculated values to zero, mitigating this drawback, but it provides a smaller weight for outliers in the data, which might affect model capacity to detect certain patterns.

C. Predictive machine-learning model

The time-series prediction algorithm consists of a simple Long Short-Term Memory network implemented using Keras. The architecture consists of the input layer, the LSTM layer and a dense layer for the prediction output. We use callbacks to slightly reduce the learning rate throughout the training epochs and to early stop if loss metrics stagnate.

Since each EEG recording file contains a relatively large amount of data, it is possible to train the model in a single file and test its performance in another, achieving satisfying results.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The testing sessions revealed that the LSTM model achieved its best performance in a narrow, single-point prediction setting, particularly when forecasting signals within lower value ranges. The application of data preprocessing proved to be a critical factor, significantly enhancing results, most notably in the Resting-state case. However, the model's success did not extend to more complex, multi-point forecasting tasks, where performance declined substantially and preprocessing routines offered no clear advantage. This performance disparity was also context-dependent; models performed better on data with predictable patterns (like Sensory Stimulation) and struggled with the inherent unpredictability of cognitive task data. Ultimately, the results indicate that while the current approach is effective for short-term, single-point predictions on preprocessed data, its efficacy is limited for broader forecasting applications, highlighting a need for methodological improvements.

The scenario that most benefited from the application of preprocessing was the Resting-state case, as it is possible to observe in Table 1. Figure 1 illustrates the influence of filtering and exclusion of a noisy component in data by comparing both the signal with and without preprocessing for this case.

Fig. 1. Signal propagation with and without preprocessing for the resting-state case.

When analyzing model predictions in a multi-signal propagation setting, it was confirmed that the utilized metric scores did not accurately reflect model performances for all

observed cases. In general, all trained models performed exceptionally well when preprocessing was applied and the task was limited to the prediction of one single point in time, as illustrated in Figure 2:

Fig. 2. Single point signal predictions (blue lines) vs real values (orange lines)

From Figure 2 it is also possible to observe that, in general, the standardization method based on normalization indicated better efficiency in improving prediction accuracy and precision, especially when the data was not preprocessed.

In contrast, when evaluating the prediction of multiple points in time, it was possible to observe significant changes in model dynamics, as illustrated in Figure 3, which highlights the best obtained results for the multipoint conditions tested:

Fig. 3. Multipoint signal predictions (blue lines) vs real values (orange lines).

TABLE 1. Model performances for each dataset and testing condition

s	1		5		10		30	
	MSE	MAE	MSE	MAE	MSE	MAE	MSE	MAE
Resting-state								
Filter and ICA (scaled)	0.001	0.08	1.3	0.61	12.418	2.212	32.0813	4.1232
Raw data (scaled)	0.79	0.75	0.79	0.75	0.79	0.75	0.0276	0.1315
Filter and ICA (normalized)	2.95E-05	0.004	0.001	0.021	4.42E-10	1.68E-05	0.0695	0.188
Raw data (normalized)	0.0029	0.04	0.007	0.064	9.99E-06	9.99E-04	0.0153	0.0942
Sensory stim.								
ICA (scaled)	1.73E-05	0.0029	0.0279	0.058	0.0228	0.0962	1.7733	0.7704
Raw data (scaled)	7.28E-07	7.94E-04	3.58E-06	0.0014	8.81E-06	0.0019	4.23E-04	0.0126
ICA (normalized)	1.91E-05	0.003	0.0059	0.0483	2.83E-04	0.0109	0.0191	0.0806
Raw data (normalized)	1.96E-05	0.0031	6.42E-05	0.0056	2.80E-04	0.0108	9.30E-06	0.0022
Cognition								
ICA (scaled)	0.0186	0.0739	0.0259	0.1029	0.1088	0.2191	0.3629	0.4387
Raw data (scaled)	6.40E-06	0.0016	2.30E-02	9.56E-02	0.1115	0.2228	0.3595	0.4358
ICA (normalized)	5.59E-04	0.0178	0.022	0.0931	0.1017	0.2123	0.3433	0.4258
Raw data (normalized)	6.33E-04	0.0164	0.0236	0.0969	0.1035	0.2155	0.3364	0.4209
Seizure								
Filter (scaled)	0.0467	0.1281	0.7005	0.545	1.3536	0.7779	2.8751	1.0886
Raw data (scaled)	0.0957	0.1988	0.6842	0.5521	1.3772	0.791	2.8742	1.0905
Filter (normalized)	0.0083	0.0578	0.0938	0.2019	0.2036	0.3022	0.4301	0.4221
Raw data (normalized)	0.0142	0.0774	0.1021	0.2144	0.2079	0.308	0.4377	0.425

From Figure 2, it is possible to conclude that the positive results obtained previously, where the prediction was limited to one point, are not generalizable for wider settings. When predicting multiple unseen values, the employed preprocessing routines did not provide better training results, and it is not possible to observe any significant differences in performance from the two standardization methods. In general, it is noticeable that there is not a uniform tendency for the predictive behavior of each model across the different contexts, although some observations may be presented:

Poor performances were especially evident for the resting-state and cognitive task cases. This may be due to (1) the sampling rate and complete lack of initial signal manipulation from the resting-state case, and (2) the remarkably unpredictable nature of brain activity associated with the execution of a task with high cognitive load. In both the sensory stimulation and seizure examination (another type of resting-state, since no seizures occurred during these observations) scenarios, brain activity is expected to generate more detectable patterns. Prediction performance for the sensory stimulation case also may have been improved by having a significantly higher sampling rate (it is easy to notice that the signal dynamics seem more stable) and by the limited number of channels, which focused only on a specific brain region (the occipital lobe) and naturally limits signal variability. As a result, it is observable that in both scenarios, the trained models appeared to have slightly better performances in attempting to imitate signal tendencies.

It is relevant to point out that, except for the resting-state datasets, the other two tested datasets provided the data with some sort of preprocessing, which may have influenced the resulting analyses, amplifying the observable contrast in performance with the first resting-state case.

The displayed reduction in training performance may also be attributed to the loss function employed for model training, since in every analyzed case the model stopped training with very low values for loss, which usually indicates that the prediction error is low and, therefore, the model is

performing well. However, as previously mentioned, EEG signals naturally oscillate in low values, which may have posed a challenge that persisted in the more "long-term" prediction attempts even after the standardization procedures. Additionally, the process of error minimization through backpropagation may also have been affected if the loss metric was not sufficiently adequate, since the model uses the function to calculate the optimal weights in the network.

Finally, to address the raised hypotheses of potential factors hindering prediction performances, future endeavors may include: the proposition of a new loss function, which has to be especially adapted for EEG data; standardization of the frequency rate in all analyzed scenarios and exclusive evaluation of data that has not been preprocessed previously, which may be achieved by procedures of data acquisition as opposed to the utilization of publicly available datasets. In addition, more strategies may be adopted in order to improve performance via changes in model architecture, since the implemented neural network is the simplest possible form of an LSTM model.

Additionally, once the utilized metric scores are better standardized, it will also be possible to statistically analyze the differences between experimental settings, which is a valuable enhancement for model evaluation in future works.

IV. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS

A. *Conflict of Interest*

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

B. *Statement of informed Consent and human rights*

All the utilized resources of biomedical data were collected following standard ethical proceedings, including the informed consent of participants. Most of the data were

also made publicly available and may be freely used for research.

V. CONCLUSION

Upon the completion of all proposed analysis routines, it is possible to conclude that the evaluated LSTM model presented positive performances for single-value predictions, but the results are not generalizable for multipoint predictions.

It was observed that the preprocessing techniques effectively improved model performances in the success cases, but might have potentialized the challenges for some less conclusive scenarios, thus indicating that their utilization is generally good, but might produce unexpected outcomes when the context of prediction is too complex.

From the evaluated conditions, it was possible to observe various aspects in which the quality of the data may affect model performance for the tested architecture of LSTM neural network. Therefore, it was possible to raise hypotheses regarding the main factors of influence, enabling us to propose means to further optimize model training for time series prediction of EEG signals in future works.

As a potential contribution for public health applications centered in EEG, the investigation of adequate methods of signal processing and evaluation of the main factors of influence for predictive model performance may be relevant to assure that the employment of EEG-based examinations in real-world scenarios provides reliable and efficient treatments.

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